

Comparism of Serum Epidermal Growth Factor receptor and Cyclooxygenase-2 levels in patients with Non-small Cell Carcinoma of Lung and Normal Subjects

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Abstract

Relation of inflammation and cancer can be proven in most of the studies. Epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) overexpression is one of the commonest causes of non-small cell carcinoma of lung cancer (NSCLC). Cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) enzyme and its products; prostaglandin, prostacyclin, thromboxane are involved in inflammation. The aim of the study was to compare the serum epidermal growth factor receptor and cyclooxygenase-2 levels between patients with non-small cell carcinoma of lung and healthy controls. This study included 53 patients diagnosed as NSCLC and 16 apparently healthy controls. In 53 patients, 3 patients were diagnosed as adenocarcinoma and 50 patients were diagnosed as squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) of lung. In both subjects, serum EGFR and COX-2 levels were determined by ELISA.

The mean serum EGFR and COX-2 levels of NSCLC patients were significantly higher than those of healthy controls (170.10 ± 13.80 vs. 3.56 ± 0.48 ng/ml) and (13.21 ± 3.17 vs. 0.62 ± 0.15 ng/ml) respectively ($p < 0.001$ in both). Both the mean serum EGFR and COX-2 levels of SCC patients (172.10 ± 14.30 ng/ml and 13.60 ± 3.34 ng/ml) were significantly higher than those of healthy controls ($p < 0.001$ in both).

Both serum EGFR levels and COX-2 levels of patients with adenocarcinoma of lung (137.40 ± 64.70 ng/ml and 6.69 ± 5.52 ng/ml) were not significant different with those of healthy controls ($p = 0.174$ and $p = 0.386$) respectively.

The mean serum EGFR and COX-2 levels of SCC patients were higher than those of adenocarcinoma patients but they were not significant ($p = 0.653$ and $p = 0.363$) respectively. These findings indicated that EGFR and COX-2 play an important role in carcinogenesis of lung.

INTRODUCTION

Carcinoma of the lung is leading cause of death world wide and has a poor prognosis. Dysregulation of key pathways involved in cellular growth and apoptosis results in tumorigenesis. Epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) is one of the products of protooncogenes. EGFR is a kind of receptor tyrosine kinase expressed on the surface of epithelial cells. EGFR regulates vital cellular processes such as proliferation, migration, survival and angiogenesis.⁷

Many chronic skin inflammation or irritations are known to be associated with increased prevalence of squamous cell carcinoma.¹⁴ Cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) is an inducible enzyme stimulated by cytokines, growth factors, oncogenes, or tumor promoters during inflammation or malignancy. The carcinogenic effect of COX-2 mainly exerted through the increase level of prostaglandin.² It results in decreased apoptosis, increased tumor invasiveness, immunosuppression and angiogenesis.⁹

Involvement of these two molecules in carcinogenesis is determined by immunohistochemistry (IHC) method in vitro studies or cancers other than lung cancer. In this study, determination of EGFR and COX-2 levels were done by ELISA methods in the serum of patients with NSCLC.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It was cross-sectional descriptive study conducted from December 2010 to June 2014. A total 53 numbers of patients diagnosed as NSCLC by histology and cytology reports by pathologist were collected from Department of Respiratory Medicine and Department of Thoracic Surgery, Yangon General Hospital were included. Sixteen numbers of apparently healthy adults who lived in Lanmadaw Township and worked at Department of Biochemistry, University of Medicine 1, Yangon were selected as control. Both men and women patients and normal subjects were included. But the patients who have renal or hepatic failure with high serum creatinine or liver enzymes, pulmonary tuberculosis, autoimmune disease, other inflammatory diseases and other malignancies and patients who were taking NSAID and or steroid drugs within 3 weeks were excluded from the study.

After taking informed consent, history taking and physical examination, 5 ml of blood were collected and serum were stored at -80°C before analysis. Determination of serum EGFR and COX-2 were done at Nuclear Medicine Research Division, Department of Medical Research (Lower Myanmar) by ELISA method which was a quantitative sandwich immunoassay and both kits were products of Uscn Life Science, USA.

Data entry was done in Microsoft Excel and data analysis was done by using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software version 16. Standard statistical methods were applied for the calculation of mean, standard error of the mean and standard deviation. Comparison of the serum EGFR and COX-2 levels was analyzed by unpaired t test. Significant level was decided if the probability levels of all tests were <0.05.

Ethical consideration

The proposal of this research was approved by Ethic and Research Committee, University of Medicine 1 on 18th January, 2012.

RESULTS

Table 1. Comparison of Serum EGFR and COX -2 levels of healthy control and NSCLC patients

Parameter	Mean ± SEM (Range)		Probability
Serum EGFR level (ng/ml)	Healthy control (n=16) 3.56 ± 0.48 (0.19 - 5.47)	NSCLC patients (n = 53) 170.10 ± 13.80 (4.14 - 439.20)	p < 0.001
	Healthy control (n=16)	SCC patients (n=50) 172.10 ± 14.30 (4.14 - 439.20)	p < 0.001
	Healthy control (n=16)	Adenocarcinoma patients (n = 3) 137.40 ± 64.70 (64.70 - 266.40)	p = 0.174
	SCC patients (n=50)	Adenocarcinoma patients (n = 3)	p = 0.653
Serum COX-2 level (ng/ml)	Healthy control (n=16) 0.62 ± 0.15 (0.00 - 2.03)	NSCLC patients (n = 53) 13.21 ± 3.17 (0.49 - 145.70)	p < 0.001
	Healthy control (n=16)	SCC patients (n=50) 13.60 ± 3.34 (0.49 - 145.70)	p < 0.001
	Healthy control (n=16)	Adenocarcinoma patients (n = 3) 6.69 ± 5.52 (0.78 - 17.73)	p = 0.386
	SCC patients (n=50)	Adenocarcinoma patients (n = 3)	p = 0.363

Age (mean \pm SD) of healthy controls, patients with NSCLC, SCC and adenocarcinoma of lung are 56.38 ± 10.17 years (range = 40-73 years), 60.83 ± 9.62 years (range = 27-79 years), 60.66 ± 9.85 years (range = 27-79 years) and 63.67 ± 3.51 years (range = 60-67 years) respectively. There is no significant difference in age between healthy controls and patients with NSCLC or SCC or adenocarcinoma of lung ($p = 0.134$, $p = 0.152$ and $p = 0.052$) respectively. In healthy control group, majority (63%) is female but in NSCLC patients, majority (70%) is male.

DISCUSSION

Lung cancer was the most commonly diagnosed cancer world wide and had 13.0% (1.8 million) of the total new cancer cases. It was also the most common causes of cancer death and had 19.4% (1.6 million) of the total cancer-related deaths.⁵

For therapeutic purposes, carcinomas of the lung are classified into two broad groups: small cell lung cancer (SCLC) and non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). SCLC and NSCLC are clinically and genetically distinct. SCLCs are best treated by chemotherapy because all are metastatic to other tissues. By contrast, NSCLCs are curable by surgery if limited to the lung.

EGFR normally involves in cell growth, proliferation, cell division, differentiation and apoptosis. Over-expression or mutation of EGFR activates cellular signaling pathways that induce characteristics of cancer cells, including angiogenesis, metastasis, and invasiveness. Thus EGFR is as target of therapy and have been implicated in disease progression, decreased survival, and resistance to cytotoxic agents or radiation. COX-2 and its products prostaglandin are known to play an important role in carcinogenesis by stimulating growth, survival, invasion, metastasis, and angiogenesis of tumor cells.

In the present study, the mean serum EGFR level in healthy control was 3.56 ± 0.48 ng/ml and in NSCLC patients was 170.10 ± 13.8 ng/ml. The mean serum EGFR level of NSCLC patients was significantly higher than that of healthy controls ($p < 0.001$). The mean serum EGFR level in SCC lung patients was also significantly higher than that of healthy controls ($p < 0.001$). Although the mean serum EGFR level of adenocarcinoma patients was higher than that of healthy controls, it could not be concluded statistically significant because the number of adenocarcinoma patients was only 3.

The similar results were seen in other studies however the method of EGR determination was different. In China, Zhu et al (2010) and Li et al (2011) reported that EGFR expression in primary lung cancer tissues was significantly higher than those of the control although EGFR expression was detected by IHC method.^{17&11} In the study of Fujino, the mean EGFR level in primary non-small cell lung cancer tissues was significantly higher than in normal tissues but serum EGFR level was measured by using a competitive radioligand binding assay.⁶

Increased serum EGFR level in carcinoma of lung may be due to EGFR over-expression. Over-expression of EGFR can occur by amplification or mutation of EGFR gene. But Dacic et al (2006) found that EGFR over-expression in NSCLC was uncoupled with gene amplification. Three polymorphisms that are associated with EGFR over-expression are a polymorphic dinucleotide repeat (CA simple sequence repeat 1 [CA-SSR1]) in intron one (lower number of repeats) and two single nucleotide polymorphisms in the promoter region, -216 (G/T or T/T) and -191 (C/A or A/A).¹²

There were also other studies which results were inconsistent with those of the present study. In the study of Lemos-Gonzalez and colleagues (2007), the mean serum EGFR level of NSCLC patients was significantly decreased than that of healthy subjects.¹⁰ Schneider et al

(1999) found that there was no significant difference in serum EGFR levels in patients with lung caners and healthy controls.¹³

Decreased or no difference in serum EGFR level in carcinoma of lung may be due to different activity of metalloprotease enzymes. EGFR extracellular domains and its ligands are shed from membrane by membrane anchored proteases, a family of A Disintegrin And Metalloproteinase (ADAM). The proteolytic activity of ADAM can be influenced by factors such as osmotic and mechanical stress, G protein-coupled receptor activation, activation of protein kinase C, increase in intracellular calcium, serum factors and growth factors.¹⁶

In the present study, serum EGFR levels in patients with SCC of the lung were higher than those of patients with adenocarcinoma lung but it can't be compared because the number of adenocarcinoma lung patients was only 3. The similar pattern of result was obtained however EGFR expression was determined on tumor cells by IHC method rather than ELISA. In the study of Veale et al (1993) in which EGFR was most commonly found in SCC (70%) followed by adenocarcinoma (50%). Dacic and coworkers (2006) also found that EGFR protein expression was more common in SCC (26.2%) than in adenocarcinoma (11.1%) ($p = 0.0076$). EGFR expression in SCC of lung was more frequently associated with EGFR amplification than adenocarcinoma lung (14.5%) vs (3.6%) cases ($p = 0.0208$).

In the present study, the mean serum COX-2 level of NSCLC patients (0.62 ± 0.15 ng/ml) was significantly higher than that of healthy controls (13.21 ± 3.17 ng/ml) ($p < 0.001$). In most of the studies, COX-2 expression was detected by IHC in lung tissues rather than serum by ELISA. Li and colleagues (2011) found that COX-2 expression was 90% for NSCLC tumors and was significantly higher than that for normal lung (0%).¹¹ Zhu, Liu and Wang (2010) detected that COX-2 expression in primary lung cancer tissues (52.8%) was significantly higher than those of the control ($P < 0.05$).¹⁷

In the present study, mean serum COX-2 level in patients with SCC of the lung was higher than that of patients with adenocarcinoma of the lung but it was not significant ($p = 0.363$). It was not consistent with the studies that COX-2 expression was found more in adenocarcinoma than SCC of lung.^{8,11}

The higher serum COX-2 level in SCC than adenocarcinoma of lung in the present study may be due to large difference in number of cases between adenocarcinoma cases ($n=3$) and SCC cases ($n=50$). Another explanation for this discrepancy was COX-2 expression was measured by IHC in the previous studies and serum COX-2 was measured by ELISA in the present study. Since COX-2 enzyme is located at the luminal side of the endoplasmic reticulum and nuclear membrane, it can't be detected in the serum until the cells are destroyed.¹ Therefore serum COX-2 level may not reflect its actual expression in cancer cells.

The findings of the present study indicated that both EGFR and COX-2 have implication in development of NSCLC and can be applied in further research in relation between cancer and inflammation. But in the present study, EGFR and COX-2 expressions couldn't be measured in the tissue samples. Therefore applicability of measuring serum COX-2 is not sure although measuring serum EGFR is applicable in the further study.

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REFERENCES

1. Chandrasekharan NV and Simmons DL. (2004) The cyclooxygenases. *Genome Biology*; **5**: 241.
2. Choe MS, Zhang X, Shin HJC, Shin DM, and Chen Z. Interaction between epidermal growth factor receptor- and cyclooxygenase 2 -mediated pathways and its implications for the chemoprevention of head and neck cancer. *Molecular Cancer Therapeutics* 2005; **4**: 1448-1455.
3. Dacic S, Flanagan M, Cieply K, Ramalingam S, Luketich J, Belani C and Yousem SA. Significance of EGFR Protein Expression and Gene Amplification in Non-Small Cell Lung Carcinoma. *American Journal of Clinical Pathology* 2006; **125**: 860-865.
4. Dang TP and Carbone DP. Cancer of the Lung. In: *Devita, Hellman & Rosenberg's Cancer: Principles & Practice of Oncology*. 8th Edition. ed. DeVita VT, Lawrence TS, Rosenberg SA, 2008; p. 888-895. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
5. Ferlay J, Soerjomataram I, Ervik M, Dikshit R, Eser S, Mathers C, Rebelo M, Parkin DM, Forman D, Bray F. GLOBOCAN 2012 volume 1.0, Cancer Incidence and Mortality Worldwide. *International Agency for Research on Cancer* 2013; *Cancer Base No.* 11.
6. Fujino S, Enokibori T, Tezuka N, Asada Y, Inoue, S Kato H. and A. Mori A. A Comparison of Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor Levels and Other Prognostic Parameters in Non-small Cell Lung Cancer. *European Journal of Cancer* 1996r; **32A (12)**: 2070-2074.
7. Hazzalin CA, Mahadevan LC. MAPK-regulated transcription: a continuously variable gene switch? *Nature Reviews Molecular Cell Biology* 2002; **3**: 30-40.
8. Hida T, Yatabe Y, Achiwa H, Muramatsu H, Kozaki K, Nakamura S, Ogawa M, Mitsudomi T, Sugiura T, Takahashi T. Increased expression of cyclooxygenase 2 occurs frequently in human lung cancers, specifically in adenocarcinomas. *Cancer Research* 1998; **58**: 3761-3764.
9. Jia RP, Xu LW, Su Q, Zhao JH, Li WC, Wang F, Xu Z. Cyclooxygenase-2 expression is dependent upon epidermal growth factor receptor expression or activation in androgen independent prostate cancer. *Asian Journal of Andrology* 2008; **10 (5)**: 758-764.
10. Lemos-González Y, Rodríguez-Berrocal FJ, Cordero OJ, Gómez C. and Cadena MP. Alteration of the serum levels of the epidermal growth factor receptor and its ligands in patients with non-small cell lung cancer and head and neck carcinoma *British Journal of Cancer* 2007; **96**: 1569-1578.
11. Li F, Liu Y, Chen H, Liao D, Shen Y, Xu F, Wang J. EGFR and COX-2 protein expression in non-small cell lung cancer and the correlation with clinical features, *Journal of Experimental & Clinical Cancer Research* 2011; **30**: 27.
12. Nomura M, Shigematsu H, Li L, Suzuki M, Takahashi T, Estess P, Siegelman M, Feng Z, Kato H, Marchetti A, Shay JW, Spitz MR, Wistuba II, Minna JD, Gazdar AF. Polymorphisms, Mutations, and Amplification of the EGFR Gene in Non-Small Cell Lung Cancers. *Public Library of Science Medicine* 2007; **4 (4)**: e125.
13. Schneider J, Presek P, Braun A, Bauer P, Konietzko N, Wiesner B and Voitowitz HJ. p53 protein, EGF receptor, and anti-p53 antibodies in serum from patients with occupationally derived lung cancer. *British Journal of Cancer* 1999; **80(12)**: 1987-1994.

14. Trinchieri G. Etiology of Cancer: Inflammation. *In: Devita, Hellman & Rosenberg's Cancer: Principles & Practice of Oncology*. 8th Edition. ed. DeVita VT, Lawrence TS, Rosenberg SA 2008, p. 192-201. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
15. Veale D, Kerr N, Gibson GJ, Kelly PJ, Harris AL. The relationship of quantitative epidermal growth factor receptor expression in non-small cell lung cancer to long term survival. *British Journal of Cancer* 1993; **68**: 162-165.
16. Weber S and Saftig P. Ectodomain shedding and ADAMs in development. *Development* 2012; **139**: 3693-3709.
17. Zhu C, Liu J and Wang X. Detection of EGFR and COX-2 Expression by Immunohistochemical Method on a Tissue Microarray Section in Lung Cancer and Biological Significance. *Chinese Journal of Lung Cancer* 2010; **13 (2)**: 107-111.